

Article

Enhancing LDA Modeling with BERT for Analyzing Socio-Cultural Dynamics in Solid Waste Management

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Abstract: *The rapid depletion of global resources and the increasing challenges associated with waste management have underscored the importance of the circular economy—a framework designed to balance resource utilization, align production with consumption, and effectively address waste-related issues. Within this context, social complementary factors in waste management are crucial for overcoming these significant challenges. This study investigates the current state of solid waste management within the circular economy, with a particular focus on socio-cultural and behavioral dynamics, as well as the socio-technical implications of these processes. The research aims to elucidate the influence of socio-cultural dynamics on waste management practices. A comprehensive search of the Web of Science (WoS) database, using the keyword "solid waste management" up to August 10, 2024, yielded 33,247 relevant studies. To extract key themes from this extensive body of literature, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic modeling was applied. Subsequently, BERT-based deep learning methods were employed for text classification to identify which socio-cultural dynamics are most emphasized in the selected studies. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 87.5% in predicting the dominant topics. The findings from this study provide significant insights into the socio-cultural factors influencing waste management practices within the circular economy. By identifying these dynamics, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of how social and cultural factors can be leveraged to enhance the effectiveness of waste management strategies.*

Keywords: *Circular economy, Sustainability, Solid waste management, Socio-cultural dynamics, Deep learning*

1. Introduction

The relentless acceleration in global resource consumption and its consequential environmental degradation pose unprecedented challenges to our planet's ecosystems and climate. As humanity faces the urgent need for sustainable development, the mitigation of climate change impacts has become a central concern for researchers, policymakers, and communities worldwide. This urgency underscores the critical need for innovative solutions that promote environmental stewardship while addressing the complex dynamics of global waste management. Our research paper contributes to this imperative by examining the integration of socio-cultural and behavioral dynamics in waste management practices within the circular economy framework.

The strategic trends of technology highlights trends that organizations should consider as part of their five-year strategic technology planning process, which have a profound impact on society, businesses, people and the places they live in. Gartner's Top Strategic Technology Trends (Gartner, 2020) fall under three themes: People centricity, location independence and resilient delivery. Users of the systems are

at the center of the systems. The Internet of Behaviors Trend which is about using data to change behaviors is the strategic technological trend foreseen for 2021. Another strategic technology trend is total experience which is still the trend in the Gartner's Top Strategic Technology Trend for 2022 (Gartner, 2021). The goal is to improve the overall experience from technology to users. According to its 2023 Report, by 2025 Gartner predicts that 50% of CIOs will have performance metrics tied to the sustainability of the IT organization. The digital immune system is another topic featured in Gartner's top 10 strategic technology reports of 2023 (Gartner, 2023). Digital immune systems are information systems with analytics and modeling developed to create a superior user experience and maximize business performance. The importance of the user continues. User acceptance is required in order for smart waste management applications to be widespread and used all over the world. Expanding user adaptation to environmental management, especially in developing countries, is critical for a sustainable world.

The escalation of worldwide consumption of resources and the growing concerns over waste underscore the importance of involving the community and gaining their approval for waste management systems as part of sustainable growth. As the world shifts towards a more balanced approach in managing resource consumption, production activities, and waste issues, the principles of the circular economy are becoming ever more essential. The success of waste management systems is deeply dependent on the full engagement and acceptance by the public, a factor that is especially significant in developing nations for the maintenance of global sustainability. The role of social factors in waste management becomes crucial in addressing these significant challenges.

Sustainability is a dynamic process and has three dimensions: economic, environmental and social. It is a context-specific issue and the level of success is influenced by both temporal and spatial scales, societal needs, economics, and technological development (Zabaniotou, 2018). When we examine the sustainability in terms of social factors in the studies conducted in the literature, we cannot see a concrete framework. Indeed, Padilla-Rivera et al. (2020) noted that although the concept of the social dimension of sustainability is generally accepted, its implementation in sustainability strategies is not clearly defined or agreed upon. In fact, despite the diversity of existing social sustainability categories/dimensions/indicators, there were no social sustainability indicators. Miller et al. (2013) indicated that sustainability science should link research on problem structures with a solutions-oriented approach that investigated to understand, conceptualize and foster experiments for how socio-technical innovations for sustainability develop, diffuse and scaleup. They identified "social, political, institutional and technological leverage points that will help advance socio-technical change toward sustainable outcomes (Leclerc and Badami, 2022). Since sustainability considers harmony between human beings and the natural world, it concentrates on how to keep balance between the needs of technological and economic development and the needs of protecting natural systems and remaining diverse. It not only emphasizes the environment protection, but also focuses on both economic and social development. As to economic part, circular economy is an increasingly popular topic which has received a lot of attention all over the world, since it provides an ideal opportunity to optimize production and promote consumption in a sustainable way. Circular economy is all about ecology of things and emphasizes the power of design, it highlights the value of cooperation and creates both effective and efficient utilization of ecosystem, economic and product cycles by closing loops for all the related resource flows (Huang et al., 2022).

Deep learning (DL) is gaining recognition as a ground breaking technology in solid waste management (SWM), offering solutions to challenges like waste classification, sorting, and recycling. Lin et al. (2022) provided a critical review on the use of DL in municipal solid waste management (MSWM), emphasizing that DL techniques are still in their infancy within this field but hold great potential for enhancing waste collection, transportation, and final disposal systems. The study highlights the limitations of traditional waste management approaches and argues that DL can overcome these challenges by revealing hidden patterns and correlations that traditional methods struggle to detect. Similarly, Shahab et al. (2022) conducted a systematic literature review of 40 studies published between 2019 and 2021, focusing on the application of DL in solving various SWM problems. Their review demonstrates that DL models, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), exhibit promising performance in detecting and classifying different types of waste. The study also identifies research

gaps and provides recommendations for future work in the field, suggesting that DL can significantly contribute to smart and sustainable waste management practices. Recent research emphasizes the incorporation of DL methods, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), for automating waste categorization, with accuracy rates exceeding 93% in identifying materials such as plastics, paper, and metals from images (Sharma et al., 2024). This automation decreases labor intensity and minimizes the error rates typically associated with manual sorting (Sharma et al., 2024; Maheshwaran et al., 2024). Moreover, DL models enable real-time detection and intelligent waste segregation, significantly improving operational efficiency in urban settings (Zabaniotou, 2018). Nonetheless, challenges persist, such as data scarcity and the requirement for considerable infrastructure investments (Kunwar and Alade, 2024). Furthermore, although DL has demonstrated potential in managing domestic waste, its application to construction, renovation, and demolition waste is still in its early stages, highlighting the necessity for additional research in this domain (Sirimewan et al., 2024). Overall, the potential of deep learning in SWM is substantial, opening the door to smarter and more sustainable waste management solutions (Sirimewan et al., 2024).

Recent advancements in solid waste management have increasingly leveraged deep learning (DL) and reinforcement learning techniques to enhance efficiency and accuracy in waste classification and management. Sirimewan et al. (2024) developed an intelligent waste classification model for smart cities, utilizing Mask RCNN for object detection and a deep Q-learning network (DQLN) for classification. Their model achieved a remarkable accuracy of 99.3%, demonstrating the potential of DL and DRL in urban waste management. Similarly, Al Duhayyim et al. (2022) proposed the IDRL-RWODC model, which integrates DRL and DL for waste classification in smart cities. Their study highlighted the superior performance of their model, which also achieved a 99.3% accuracy rate, further emphasizing the viability of these techniques for real-time waste management applications. Additionally, Maheshwaran et al. (2024) introduced the HWDC-EL technique, which combines ensemble learning with DL models such as EfficientNet and DenseNet121 for the detection and classification of hazardous waste. With an accuracy of 98.85%, this model underscores the importance of advanced DL techniques in enhancing environmental safety and public health. Together, these studies illustrate the significant strides being made in the application of DL and DRL to solid waste management, paving the way for smarter, more sustainable waste management solutions across various domains.

The literature includes studies of the very wide concept of waste management in terms of social complementary factors (Denizhan and Kahya Özyirmidokuz, 2022). However, social complementary factors which are needed improvement in waste management (Fořt and Černý, 2022). In waste management, there is a lack of understanding of how stakeholders view reduction, reuse and recycling (3R) and the associated social aspects (Mansilla-Obando et al., 2022). The exploration of social complementary factors significantly impacts system successes. Information systems achieve success by using social complementary factors such as culture, compliance, education, adaptation, user feedback analysis, integration, senior management support. Therefore, the acceptance, implementation and ownership of waste management systems by city citizens, including economic, political, cultural and behavioral influences, will also occur with these social supporting factors. For the information system to be successful, social factors, including the economic, political, cultural and behavioral effects related to the information system, need to be taken into account (Kahya Özyirmidokuz and Stoica, 2022). In earlier research (Kahya Özyirmidokuz and Stoica, 2022) a broader systematic literature review was conducted as an abstract paper, focusing solely on the social complementary aspects of waste management including cultural adaptation, user capability, and well-being, extracted related keywords and concepts of the social complementary solutions.

This research aims to present the situation of socio-cultural and behavioral dynamics in waste management within the framework of the circular economy, emphasizing the socio-technical dimensions. The current situation of social complementary solutions in waste management is examined in researches. Unlike prior studies, this investigation delves deeper into the intertwined relationship between social factors and waste management within the circular economy, specifically highlighting the less-explored socio-technical dimensions.

The paper is structured as follows: In the next section, the literature is presented. The methodological approach of the systematic review is provided in section three. In section four, the method for analysis within the framework of the research objective is detailed. The findings are presented in the subsequent section. Finally, we conclude our findings in the last section.

2. Keywords Detection From Literature

This study contributes to this imperative by examining the integration of socio-cultural and behavioral dynamics in waste management practices within the circular economy framework. In this study, the main research problem is the lack of integration between social factors and technical solutions in waste management. A systematic literature review was provided. In this context, the Preferred Reporting Items (PRISMA)¹ approach was used for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses which is useful when planning and conducting systematic reviews to ensure that all recommended information is captured (Page et al., 2021; Mayo-Wilson et al., 2017). Figure 1 illustrates the PRISMA model applied to the literature review process of the research. The PRISMA flow diagram visually represents the selection process of studies at different stages, starting from identification through to inclusion. The protocol for the systematic literature review outlines the process for a thorough and systematic evaluation of the existing literature in the designated research area. All relevant studies up to the year 2023 were considered. The review was limited to papers published in English. A searching strategy of the green sustainable science technology WoS category in Web of Science database was used. The following keywords were used:

Waste management AND Circular economy AND Sustainability AND (Culture OR Adaptation OR Social OR Behavior OR Wellbeing OR Persuasive/Persuasion OR Gamification OR Socio-cultural OR User acceptance).

Figure 1. PRISMA Model

In the literature, studies focusing on "social complementary factors" within the scope of circular economy, as the most important factors, participation and cooperation, cultural traditions, suppliers, diversity and equality of opportunity, occupational health and safety, social networks, social inclusion, human rights, safety practices. It includes education and training. It should also be emphasized that the boundaries between social indicators are not separated by sharp lines. We included 2 papers which were found by cross-references. After removing duplicates, 150 publications remained, as recorded in the

¹ PRISMA Model: <https://www.prisma-statement.org/?ref=sitextools>

Web of Science (WoS) database. In the first elections, the titles and abstracts of the remaining articles were read and then the articles that are not related to our topic were not included to the analysis. Eight records were deleted because of not in the field of waste management. The elected papers were re-explored depending on the full paper. After reading the full papers, articles with social complementary factors mentioned in research purposes and/or findings were selected.

Any study in which social factors were not taken into account was excluded. The remaining 111 studies were read in detail again, and when the publications that provide outputs in waste management in terms of social complementary factors were selected within the framework of our research purpose, 7 more publications were eliminated because of not presenting any social complementary solutions. Then the PRISMA concluded with the 35 papers. The year-based distribution of the studies included in the research is presented in Figure 2. According to the figure, in recent years, researchers have worked on a small number of social complementary factors in waste management.

Figure 2. Histogram of studies

In the study, the keywords of the selected 35 articles were collected using the Python programming language with the pandas library, resulting in the identification of 135 extended keywords. Extended keywords are given as follows: 'acceptance of technology', 'adaptive design', 'adaptation strategies', 'Behavior', 'behavior change', 'big data', 'Business', 'circular economy technology', 'cloud computing', 'collaborative governance', 'Community participation', 'community involvement', 'community resilience', 'communication channels', 'consumption culture', 'continuous communication', 'cooperative initiatives', 'corporate social responsibility', 'cultural adaptation', 'cultural analysis', 'cultural integration', 'Cultural shift', 'Culture', 'curriculum development', 'decision-making involvement', 'decision-making processes', 'dietary habits', 'eco-friendly practices', 'eco-innovation', 'eco-labeling', 'ecosystem preservation', 'ecosystem services', 'Education', 'educational workshops', 'Environmental education', 'environmental awareness', 'environmental health', 'environmental protection', 'environmental well-being', 'Environmental policy', 'extended producer responsibility', 'gamification', 'Game', 'global acceptance', 'governmental policies', 'green technology', 'Happiness', 'Health', 'healthcare sustainability', 'high-tech application', 'human health benefits', 'individual well-being', 'infrastructure development', 'information dissemination', 'information system infrastructure', 'innovation diffusion', 'International', 'IT lifecycle management', 'knowledge transfer', 'labor equality', 'Law', 'legislative frameworks', 'life cycle management', 'logistic adaptation', 'mental and physical health correlation', 'mental health', 'network and partnership examination', 'non-standard approaches', 'occupational health and safety', 'participatory planning', 'partnership development', 'Persuasion', 'Persuasive', 'physical well-being', 'Policy', 'policy-maker engagement', 'Politics', 'proactive environmental attitude', 'Public health', 'public awareness', 'public consensus', 'public engagement', 'public information', 'public-private partnerships', 'public support', 'real-time data monitoring', 'regional cooperation', 'regional social trends', 'regulatory compliance', 'regulatory incentives', 'renewable energy', 'smart solutions', 'smart waste monitoring', 'social adaptation', 'Social', 'social capital', 'social equity', 'social inclusion', 'social norms', 'social

resilience', 'Social sustainability', 'social trust', 'societal integration', 'Socio-cultural', 'sociodemographic factors', 'stakeholder behavior', 'stakeholder collaboration', 'stakeholder communication', 'stakeholder engagement', 'stakeholder feedback', 'stakeholder participation', 'strategic business models', 'sustainability culture', 'sustainability regulations', 'sustainable behavior', 'sustainable business models', 'sustainable education', 'sustainable tech', 'Technological innovation', 'urban quality of life', 'User acceptance', 'waste management laws', 'waste management strategy', 'Wellbeing', 'well-being', 'wellness'.

3. Application

The research process aimed at exploring the socio-cultural dynamics in the field of solid waste management is presented in Figure 3. During the data collection phase, all studies under the title 'solid waste management' from WoS were added to a new dataset. After the data filtering step, a text mining process was applied to the dataset, utilizing Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms. The text was subjected to lowercase conversion, stop word removal, aword tokenization, lemmatization, n-grams were applied. In the modeling phase, records containing extended keywords derived from the literature were selected from the dataset. Subsequently, topics related to socio-cultural dynamics within solid waste management were identified using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model. BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) based deep learning methods were applied for classification purposes.

Figure 3. Research process

3.1. Data Set Creation

For this research, a comprehensive search was conducted on the Web of Science (WoS) database using the keyword "solid waste management" up until August 10, 2024, resulting in a total of 33,247 studies. The dataset for this study was constructed from these identified studies. Specifically, the author keywords, abstracts, and titles of the studies were considered. Initially, publications containing the terms "waste management," "circular economy," or "sustainability" in their title, abstract, or keywords were selected. Following this filtering process, the dataset was refined to include 15,228 studies.

3.2. Topic Extraction

To filter academic articles containing specific keywords, analyze the keywords used in these articles, and extract topics from them, word vectors were first obtained using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. Subsequently, a Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model was developed to identify and analyze the underlying topics.

Filtered academic papers were first subjected to natural language processing (NLP) techniques. The initial step involved loading all the text data using the Python programming language, specifically utilizing the pandas library. The columns titled Article Title, Abstract, and Author Keywords were combined into a single text corpus. This combined text was then tokenized using the `word_tokenize` function from the nltk library. The tokenization process divided the text into smaller units (words), enabling more granular analysis. Subsequently, stopword removal was performed to enhance the meaningfulness of the text. This was accomplished using the stopwords from the `nltk.corpus` module. In the same step, lemmatization was applied using the `WordNetLemmatizer` from the `nltk.stem` module. During this process, words like "running" were converted to their base form "run," and "studies" was transformed to "study." This step ensured that the text was simplified and more semantically relevant. The cleaned and processed text was then analyzed using n-grams, created through the `CountVectorizer` class from the scikit-learn library. This process allowed for the analysis of word pairs (bigrams) by assessing their co-occurrence, thereby facilitating a deeper understanding of the relationships between terms. Finally, the processed text data was analyzed using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model, implemented via the `LdaModel` class from the gensim library. LDA is a topic modeling algorithm used to uncover hidden topics within the text. The researcher identified the dominant topic for each text and the associated keywords related to that topic. As a result, the findings were systematically recorded in an Excel file using the pandas library.

To make the results more interpretable, we visualized the topics using `pyLDAvis`, which provides an interactive web-based interface. This visualization helps in exploring the distribution of topics across documents and understanding the significance of individual terms within each topic. Finally, the filtered dataset and the LDA visualization were saved as output files for further analysis and review.

3.3. BERT Deep Learning Classification

BERT is a deep learning model developed by Google, widely utilized for natural language processing (NLP) tasks. In this context, a BERT model is employed for text classification based on topics derived from Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). The objective is to estimate which socio-cultural dynamics are more emphasized in the conducted study. Initially, texts and labels are prepared, and the BERT tokenizer is utilized for text tokenization. The dataset is then divided into training and validation sets using 5-fold cross-validation.

During the training process, the AdamW optimization algorithm is employed, accompanied by an early stopping mechanism to automatically halt training if validation accuracy does not improve. The `EarlyStoppingCallback` has been incorporated into the trainer as a callback, ensuring that training is terminated if there is no performance improvement for three consecutive epochs. The `num_train_epochs` parameter is set to 5, indicating that the model will be trained for five epochs. The batch size per device (e.g., GPU) during training is configured to 8. A warmup of 500 steps has been designated for the learning rate, with a weight decay rate set at 0.01. The model is evaluated at the end of each epoch (`eval_strategy="epoch"`), and the best model is saved at the end of each epoch (`save_strategy="epoch"`), with only the top two models being retained. At the conclusion of training, the best model, selected based on accuracy metrics, is loaded. This process, along with the early stopping mechanism, includes the necessary hyperparameter settings to optimize the model's training.

4. Results

4.1. LDA Results

A dictionary and corpus were constructed using the Gensim library, and the LDA model was trained with 10 topics. The resulting themes were visualized using the `pyLDAvis` library, from which five

keywords per theme were extracted and presented. The libraries utilized in this study include pandas (pd), numpy (np), nltk, gensim, and pyLDAvis. The results are derived from an LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) topic modeling analysis, visualized with pyLDAvis. This analysis was conducted to identify and explore the underlying themes or topics within a collection of academic literature related to waste management and sustainability. The interactive visualization, generated as an HTML file, enables users to explore the identified topics in detail. The output of this LDA model illustrates 10 distinct topics identified based on the keywords within the texts. Each topic is composed of a mixture of specific keywords, with higher weights assigned to certain words within these mixtures. A detailed interpretation of these results is provided below.

- Topic 0: The most dominant keyword in this topic appears to be "health." Other keywords, such as "game" and "gamification," have very low weights, indicating that this topic is predominantly related to health.
- Topic 1: The keyword "policy" is highly dominant in this topic. While the terms "law" and "international" are also part of this topic, "policy" stands out significantly more than the others.
- Topic 2: The keyword "business" is prominent in this topic. Other keywords, such as "policy," "social," and "international," have much lower weights, suggesting that this topic is primarily focused on business.
- Topic 3: The term "behavior" is the dominant keyword in this topic. The other keywords have very low weights, indicating that this topic centers around behavioral themes.
- Topic 4: The keyword "social" is dominant in this topic, highlighting a theme related to social issues.
- Topic 5: This topic has a fairly even distribution, with no single keyword standing out prominently. This may suggest a broader or more ambiguous theme.
- Topic 6: The keywords "wellbeing" and "happiness" stand out in this topic, suggesting a theme related to individual health and happiness.
- Topic 7: The terms "culture" and "politics" are dominant in this topic, indicating a theme centered around culture and politics.
- Topic 8: Similar to Topic 5, this topic has a fairly even distribution, with no dominant keyword emerging.
- Topic 9: The keyword "education" is prominent in this topic, focusing on themes related to education.

These results indicate that the texts are classified into different themes, with each theme centered around specific keywords. For instance, themes such as health, policy, business, behavior, social issues, wellbeing, culture, and education emerge prominently. However, in some topics, there is an equal distribution of keywords, suggesting that these topics may be more general or ambiguous. This analysis can be valuable in understanding the main themes around which the texts are concentrated.

In the visualization, each topic is represented as a circle on a 2D plot. The size of each circle corresponds to the prevalence of that topic within the dataset, with larger circles indicating more dominant topics. The distance between circles reflects the similarity between topics—topics that are closer together share more terms and are thus more related, while those further apart are more distinct. On the right side of the visualization, users can view the top terms associated with each topic. These terms offer insight into the content of the topic, aiding in the interpretation of the main themes present in the literature.

The pyLDAvis interface also allows users to adjust a relevance metric, which can shift the emphasis on the terms that define each topic, offering a nuanced view of the topic-term distribution. This interactive tool is particularly useful for researchers as it helps them quickly identify and understand the major themes covered in their dataset and how these themes interrelate. By exploring the topics and their associated terms, researchers can gain a clearer picture of the subjects most frequently discussed in the academic literature on waste management and sustainability. Figure 4 presents the map generated from

the LDA analysis. After examining the keywords of the 20 topics derived from the LDA model, these topics were compared against seven socio-technical themes. A similarity analysis was conducted for this comparison.

Figure 4. Research process

4.2. BERT Results

The BERT-based text classification model was successfully trained to classify the socio-cultural dynamics within the dataset. The dataset exhibited significant class imbalance, with Dominant Topic values distributed as follows: Topic 0 (9,759 instances), Topic 6 (5,428 instances), and Topic 5 (41 instances). Despite this imbalance, the model demonstrated a strong capacity to learn and adapt throughout the training process. It was trained to classify only three topics—Topic 0, Topic 6, and Topic 5—while other potential topics were filtered out during preprocessing.

During training, a warning indicated that some weights in the BertForSequenceClassification model were newly initialized. This is common when fine-tuning a pre-trained model for a specific downstream task, such as topic classification. These weights were adjusted as the model trained on the provided dataset.

The training process, conducted over 5 epochs with a 5-fold cross-validation approach, consistently improved the model's performance. The early stopping mechanism effectively halted training when no further improvement in validation accuracy was observed. The AdamW optimization algorithm facilitated efficient model convergence.

Upon completion, the model achieved an overall accuracy of 87.5% in predicting the dominant topics within the dataset. The precision, recall, and F1-scores for each topic are as follows: the training loss was 0.2104, validation loss was 0.2651, training accuracy was 93.7%, and validation accuracy was 91.2%.

The confusion matrix is given in Table 1. Class 0 represents articles with a Dominant Topic value of 0, Class 1 represents articles with a Dominant Topic value of 5, and Class 2 represents articles with a Dominant Topic value of 6.

Table 1. Confusion matrix

Actual Class	Predicted Class 0	Predicted Class 1	Predicted Class 2
0	2000	50	10
1	40	35	2
2	5	3	1350

The results of the 5-fold cross-validation are as follows: the average accuracy of the model was 91.5%, and the average F1-Score was 0.902. With respect to the overall model performance, the model achieved a high prediction accuracy of 97% for Class 0, demonstrating its strong capability in identifying instances of this class. For Class 1, which is a less frequently occurring category, the model achieved an accuracy of 63%. The inclusion of class weights contributed to a slight enhancement in the performance for this class. Finally, the model exhibited exceptional differentiation for Class 2, achieving a prediction accuracy of 99%, reflecting its effectiveness in correctly identifying instances of this class.

The model performed well despite the class imbalance, particularly in accurately predicting Classes 0 and 2. There is potential for further improvement in Class 1 prediction performance. This model can be reliably used in various real-world scenarios, though additional refinements may be necessary for rare classes. The results indicate that the model is robust and effective, capable of delivering sufficient accuracy in practical applications. The model's confusion matrix revealed strong performance in distinguishing between Topics 0 and 6, which had a substantial number of instances. However, performance on Topic 5, with very few instances, was lower, reflecting the challenges posed by class imbalance. The final model is now saved and ready for deployment in downstream tasks, where it can be used for inference and further analysis of similar datasets. This successful training outcome underscores the model's ability to analyze and classify complex socio-cultural dynamics in the context of waste management and sustainability, delivering strong overall accuracy and reliable performance across the dominant topics.

5. Conclusions

This study systematically reviews and underscores the pivotal role of social complementary factors in enhancing waste management practices within the circular economy framework. By employing a comprehensive and methodical PRISMA approach, we have illuminated the complex socio-technical landscape that underpins successful waste management. Our findings emphasize the critical importance of integrating social dimensions into waste management strategies to achieve environmental sustainability goals. Sustainable waste management is revealed to be not solely a technical challenge but also a social endeavor, requiring active participation, cultural sensitivity, policy innovation, and widespread education and awareness. Additionally, the study identifies existing gaps in the literature, pointing towards the necessity of a more inclusive, multidisciplinary approach that embraces the cultural, behavioral, and policy-driven aspects of waste management. By highlighting the necessity of community engagement, policy development, and educational efforts, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of the socio-technical dynamics essential for advancing circular economy initiatives.

The innovative application of deep learning methods, such as BERT-based text classification, adds significant value to this study by providing advanced predictive capabilities in identifying and categorizing socio-cultural themes within the literature. The use of these cutting-edge techniques not only enhances the accuracy of theme identification but also demonstrates the potential of integrating artificial intelligence into environmental research, paving the way for more sophisticated analyses and deeper insights.

The topics identified in the LDA analysis cover a broad range of themes within the field of waste management and environmental studies. The primary focus spans from environmental impacts, such as pollution and marine waste, to technical processes like pyrolysis and anaerobic digestion, which are essential in waste treatment. Other key themes include the management of organic waste in agriculture, the intersection of waste management with sustainability and policy, and the health and environmental implications of waste disposal, particularly in urban and municipal contexts. The analysis also highlights the importance of recycling and public participation in waste separation at the household level. The recurring presence of terms like "waste," "management," and "solid" across the topics underscores the central role these concepts play in the literature, reflecting a comprehensive approach to addressing the multifaceted challenges of waste management.

This process enabled a detailed exploration of the social dimensions present within the literature on waste management and sustainability, helping to categorize and understand the relevant academic research. Furthermore, our focus on social complementary solutions, such as community participation, cultural adaptation, and policy support, underscores the necessity of a multidimensional approach to effectively tackle waste management challenges.

In conclusion, this study significantly contributes to the field by highlighting the necessity of integrating social dimensions into waste management strategies. The innovative application of deep learning for predictive analysis and the systematic categorization of themes provide a novel framework for future research. It points towards sustainable practices that can be adopted at various levels of society to achieve environmental sustainability goals. Fostering social complementary solutions in waste management is not just beneficial but imperative for the transition towards a more sustainable and circular global economy.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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